

The Parasitic Infection with *Ascaris lumbricoides* in Al-Rifa'i District, Dhi Qar Province

Majid Mauff Tumaa Al-Durie

Thi-Qar Health Department, Al-Rifai Teaching Hospital, Ministry of Health, Iraq

Abstract

This study was conducted in Dhi Qar province, Al-Rifa'i district, Iraq to investigate the prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections, with particular attention to *Ascaris lumbricoides*. A total of 640 stool samples were collected from patients attending Al-Rifa'i General Hospital and selected medical centers during the period from 22 November 2025 to 20 June 2026. The ages of the participants ranged from ≤ 2 years to more than 55 years. Among the examined patients, 265 were males and 375 were females. The results showed that intestinal parasitic infections were detected in 235 patients, representing an overall prevalence of 36.71%. *Ascaris lumbricoides* were identified in 15 patients, with a prevalence rate of 2.34%. These findings indicate that intestinal parasitic infections remain an important health problem in Al-Rifa'i district and its surrounding areas. The study also highlights the need for continued epidemiological surveillance, improved sanitation, health education, and preventive control programs to reduce the burden of intestinal parasites in the community.

Keywords: *Intestinal parasitic infection, Ascaris lumbricoides, Al-Rifa'i, Dhi Qar, Iraq.*

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Introduction

Parasitic infections are among the most common infectious diseases worldwide and continue to represent a major public health concern, particularly in developing countries. It has been estimated that parasitic infections affect approximately 3.5 billion people globally and are responsible for about 450 million cases of illness. These infections are especially common in communities with limited resources, where poor sanitation, inadequate health services, and low socioeconomic conditions contribute to their persistence and spread (Tigabu et al., 2019). In addition, parasitic diseases mainly affect poor and disadvantaged populations in low- and middle-income countries, especially in tropical and subtropical regions (Thomas and Fomefret, 2015).

The high prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections in tropical and subtropical countries is associated with several environmental, social, and behavioral factors. These include increased population density, poor sanitation, inadequate toilet facilities, unsafe food and water sources, malnutrition, reduced host immunity, and environmental changes. Such factors facilitate the transmission of intestinal parasites and increase the risk of infection, particularly among children and vulnerable populations (Unasho, 2013).

In Iraq, several studies have investigated the prevalence of intestinal parasites in different provinces. In Baghdad, Bdewi (2009) reported intestinal parasitic infections among patients attending selected hospitals. Similarly, a study conducted in Al-Najaf city by Al-Shadood et al. (2009) documented the

occurrence of intestinal parasites among the examined population. However, relatively few studies have focused on Al-Rifa'i district in Dhi Qar province. Previous local studies, such as those conducted by Akram (2018) and Ali (2019), reported the presence of parasitic infections in the area, indicating the need for further epidemiological evaluation.

Based on this background, the present study was designed to determine the intestinal parasitic infections present among patients in Al-Rifa'i district and its surrounding areas in Dhi Qar province. The study also aimed to evaluate the relationship between recorded parasitic infections and selected demographic factors, including age and sex.

Ascaris lumbricoides is one of the most common soil-transmitted helminths infecting humans. It is a large intestinal roundworm that may reach up to 35 cm in length. Human infection occurs mainly through ingestion of infective eggs from contaminated food, water, soil, or hands. Because of its high reproductive capacity and environmental resistance, *A. lumbricoides* remains widely distributed in areas with poor sanitation and limited hygiene practices (Harhay et al., 2010).

Taxonomically, *Ascaris lumbricoides* belongs to Kingdom Animalia, Phylum Nematoda, and Class Chromadorea. This classification reflects its biological characteristics as a nematode parasite adapted to the human intestinal environment (Cox, 2002; Blunt, 2004).

Morphologically, adult *A. lumbricoides* worms are characterized by their large cylindrical bodies. Males are usually 2–4 mm in diameter and 15–31 cm in length, with a posterior end that is curved ventrally and ends in a bluntly pointed tail. Females are larger, measuring approximately 3–6 mm in diameter and 20–49 cm in length. A single female may contain millions of eggs in the uterus and can lay about 200,000 eggs per day. Fertilized eggs are usually oval to round in shape, measuring about 45–75 µm in length and 35–50 µm in width, and are surrounded by a thick outer shell. Unfertilized eggs are larger and may measure approximately 88–94 µm (Leles et al., 2012).

The life cycle of *A. lumbricoides* begins when fertilized eggs are passed in the feces of infected individuals. Unfertilized eggs may also be present in stool samples, but they do not develop into infective stages. Under suitable environmental conditions, fertilized eggs embryonate in the soil and become infective within 18 days to several weeks. After ingestion of infective eggs, larvae hatch in the small intestine, penetrate the intestinal wall, and enter the bloodstream. They then migrate through the liver and heart to the lungs, where they enter the alveoli and continue development. After further maturation, the larvae move upward through the respiratory tract, are swallowed, and return to the small intestine, where they develop into adult worms. Adult females can produce large numbers of eggs daily for 12–18 months. These eggs may become infective in soil and can remain viable for long periods under favorable conditions (Dold and Holland, 2011).

The pathogenic effects of *A. lumbricoides* infection vary according to the intensity of infection and the immune status of the host. Many infected individuals remain asymptomatic, especially in light infections. However, symptomatic cases may present with abdominal discomfort, nausea, or general gastrointestinal disturbances. Heavy worm burdens can lead to more serious complications, including intestinal obstruction and impaired growth in children. Respiratory symptoms such as cough may also occur during larval migration through the lungs. Ascariasis is generally treatable using appropriate anthelmintic medications prescribed by healthcare providers (Blackwell et al., 2015).

Epidemiologically, ascariasis has a worldwide distribution, with higher prevalence in tropical and subtropical regions light infections. However, symptomatic cases may present where environmental and sanitary conditions favor transmission (Bethony et al., 2006). It has been estimated that nearly one billion people are infected with *A. lumbricoides* globally, making it one of the most common helminthic infections in humans (Dold and Holland, 2011). The infection is especially common in sub-Saharan Africa, parts of the Americas, China, and East Asia. The eggs of *A. lumbricoides* are highly resistant to harsh environmental

conditions, including strong chemicals, desiccation, and low temperatures. Therefore, they may remain viable in soil for several months or even years (Roberts and Janovy, 2009). Historical evidence also indicates that *A. lumbricoides* infection has affected humans for thousands of years, as eggs have been identified in archaeological coprolites from different regions, including the Americas, Europe, Africa, the Middle East, and New Zealand, with some findings dating back more than 24,000 years (Dridelle, 2010).

Diagnosis of ascariasis is commonly performed through microscopic examination of stool samples for the detection of characteristic eggs. Because female worms produce large numbers of eggs, stool examination is usually effective, even in light infections. However, when only a small number of eggs are present, they may be missed unless stool concentration techniques are used. The detection of infertile *Ascaris* eggs is also diagnostically important because the presence of even a single female worm may have clinical significance, especially if worm migration occurs. Although serological tests for detecting antibodies against *A. lumbricoides* are available, they are generally used more often in epidemiological studies than in routine clinical diagnosis because of limitations related to cost and specificity (Lamberton and Jourdan, 2015).

Materials and Methods

Samples Collection

A total of 640 samples of stool, urine, vaginal discharge and blood were collected from persons attending to general Al-Rifa'i Hospital (Al-Rifa'i district, Dhi Qar province) through the period from 22/11/2025 to 20/6/2026. The age of persons was ranged from 1 months to more than 55 years old and the sex of them was males (265) and females (375). Some collected data were determined in questionnaire format from persons as age, sex, living area in center and in wide range of villages around Al-Rifa'i district.

Fresh fecal samples were collected in sterile containers and then transported to the laboratory for detect gastrointestinal parasites according to Zeibig (2013).

Stool Sample Examination

Macroscopic examination

Before microscopic examination of stool samples, the stool was examined by the naked eye for its characteristics such as its consistency, color, texture, Macroscopic examination has several implications and includes: consistency (formed or un-formed; liquid, semi liquid, solid) and gross abnormalities (mucoid, bloody, watery). These features can be refers clinically to the type of parasite may be detected in the sample. (Zeibig, 2013).

Microscopic Examination

Direct wet mount by using normal saline (0.9%)

Stool samples observed by the preparation of direct smear methods using clean glass slides, a small drop of normal saline (0.9%) or Iodine stain put on slide glass and mix well with a small portion of feces using wooden stick, then was put cover slides, and examined the sample under power amplify 40×&100×, (Tanyuksel and Petri, 2003).

Direct smear by using Lugol's Iodine

The method was done as follows (Salman, 2019):

- 1- A drop of lugol's iodine solution was placed on a glass slide.
- 2- Small amount of human fecal sample was put on lugol's iodine drop and mixed thoroughly using wooden stick.

- 3- Cover slip was applied with forceps or fingers.
- 4- Examination of slide under 40× & 100×, powers of microscope (Salman, 2019).

Results

Through the period from 22/11/2025 to 20/6/2026, the present study was performed in Al-Rifa'i district, Dhi Qar province to identify the parasitic infections with *A. lumbricoides* detected in 5 (0.78 %) cases whose are living in villages and no infection are recorded in city center.

Table 1. Parasitic Infections According to the Patients' Habitat

Center of Al-Rifa'i district	No. of examined	375
	No. of infected	0
	Prevalence of infection %	0
Villages of Al-Rifa'i district	No. of examined	265
	No. of infected	5
	Prevalence of infection %	1.88
Total	No. of examined	640
	No. of infected	5
	Prevalence of infection %	0.78

Parasitic Infections According to the Gender of Patients

Gastrointestinal parasitic infections

The present study revealed some gastrointestinal parasite infection in stool sample detected in 192 (30.00%) of examined patients. The prevalence of these gastrointestinal parasitic infections was higher in females 130 (34.66%) than in males 62 (23.39%) of all recorded parasite species. The nematode helminth *A. lumbricoides* were diagnosed in 5 (1.33%) of examined females, whereas no infection with this parasite was detected in the examined males

Parasitic Infections According to the Age of Patients

Gastrointestinal parasitic infections

The current study included 640 patients, 375 females and 265 males (Table1), the gastrointestinal parasitic infections detected in 192 patients of all age groups started from ≤ 2 years old to ≥ 55 years old. Infection with *A. lumbricoides* recorded in 5 patients of age group (3-5, 34-40, 41-47, 48-54, ≥ 55 years old) with 1 cases (1.15%) for each age group. However, this nematode was not detected in the age groups ≤ 2 , 6-12, 13-19, 20-26, 27-33) years old. The prevalence of infection with gastrointestinal parasitic infection in AL-Rifa'i district, Dhi Qar province according to the gender are shown in Table (3).

Table 2. Prevalence of Infection with Gastrointestinal Parasitic Infections in AL-Rifa'i District, Dhi Qar Province According to Gender

Group	Male No. of examined = 265		Female No. of examined = 375		Total No. of examined = 640	
	No. of infection	Prevalence of infection %	No. of infection	Prevalence of infection %	No. of infection	Prevalence of infection %
<i>A. lumbricoides</i>	0	0	5	1.33	5	0.78

Table 3. Prevalence of Infections with Gastrointestinal Parasites in Al-Rifa'i District, Dhi Qar Province According to the Age of Patients

Age (year)		
	No. of infected	Prevalence of infection %
≤ 2	0	0
3- 5	1	0.15
6 – 12	0	0
13 – 19	0	0
20 – 26	0	0
27 – 33	0	0
34 – 40	1	0.15
41 – 47	1	0.15
48 – 54	1	0.15
≥ 55	1	0.15

Discussion

Parasitic Infections

A. lumbricoides is considered one of the most common helminthic neglected tropical parasites with an estimation of 800 million to 1.2 billion infections worldwide (Hadush and Pal, 2016). Ascariasis exists in 149 tropical and subtropical countries across the world, costing developing economies of these countries around billions of dollars annually (Deribew *et al.*, 2017). *A. lumbricoides* was recorded in present study with low prevalence (0.78%). The infection with these helminths was only found in low socio-economic level and associated with poverty and poor living conditions because the eggs of intestinal nematodes (*A. lumbricoides*) require an extrinsic maturation period of days to weeks to be infective (Garcia, 2009). Therefore, *A. lumbricoides* infection is more common in rural regions than in urban areas where sanitation facilities are unsatisfactory. This helminth is widely distributed in humid regions. Therefore, the infection with *A. lumbricoides* occurs in urban populations (Shah and Shhidullah, 2018). In comparing with few studies carried out in Iraq, in Baghdad 0.6% (Kazim, 1986); in Kirkuk 1.87% (Haydar, 1993); in Sulaimani 0.5% (Hussein, 2003); in Erbil 0.17% (Saifaddin, 2004).

A. lumbricoides detected in 5 patients (0.78 %) from total sample had been examined 5 (1.88 %) in villages and isn't recorded in center of Al-Rifa'i district, *A. lumbricoides* infection like other helminth parasites is more common in rural regions than urban where sanitation facilities are unsatisfactory. The helminth is widely distributed in humid, temperate countries along the equator. Infection with *A. lumbricoides* also occurs in urban populations. In these communities, individuals are subjected to a vicious cycle of malnourishment and reinfections, leading to continuous morbidity (Shah and Shhidullah, 2018).

Conclusions

Different types of parasitic infections were detected in Al- Rifa'i district, Dhi Qar province, Iraq. The parasitic infections reported in 235 (36.71%) patients from a collection of a total of 640 samples.

Recommendations

First: Extending the study of parasitic infections in all areas of Dhi Qar province.

Second: Parasitic infections must be diagnosed correctly to avoid complications.

Third: Applying educational programs and preventive measures for parasitic infections.

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